

7th Helmholtz Open Science Forum: Research Software Rights Management at Helmholtz

September 2025

Report

Imprint

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HELMHOLTZ

Open Science

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HELMHOLTZ

Open Science

1 Abstract

As expressed in the Helmholtz Open Science Policy,¹ Open Research Software forms a vital element of Open Science at the Helmholtz Association. To support this endeavor, the Task Group Research Software of the Working Group Open Science² and the Helmholtz Open Science Office³ offers the Helmholtz Open Science Forum on Research Software to bring together the community and streamline efforts within the Association to support the development and maintenance of research software.

The present report documents the 7th Helmholtz Open Science Forum Research Software on "Research Software Rights Management at Helmholtz" which took place online on September 26, 2025; the 74 participants represented 16 of the 18 Helmholtz Centers.

The forum provided a practice-oriented platform for researchers, software developers, and legal experts to explore key aspects of research software governance. With a focus on licensing models, rights allocation processes within Helmholtz, and on the institutional policies guiding these processes, the event combined expert presentations with interactive workshops. Participants gained insights into best practices, legal frameworks, and implementation strategies to ensure compliant and sustainable software development in research environments.

With contributions from various Helmholtz Centers, the forum provided a valuable platform for knowledge exchange and the development of joint strategies concerning research software rights management and its implications across the Association.

Previous Helmholtz Open Science Fora on Research Software event were held in May 2021,⁴ April 2022,⁵ November 2022,⁶ May 2023,⁷ February 2024,⁸ and February 2025.⁹

¹ <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/open-science-in-helmholtz/open-science-policy/>

² <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/open-science-in-helmholtz/working-group-open-science/task-group-research-software/>

³ <https://os.helmholtz.de>

⁴ <https://os.helmholtz.de/veranstaltungen/foren/1-forum-forschungssoftware/>

⁵ <https://os.helmholtz.de/veranstaltungen/foren/2-forum-forschungssoftware/>

⁶ <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/events/fora/3rd-forum-research-software/>

⁷ <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/events/fora/4th-forum-research-software/>

⁸ <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/events/fora/5th-forum-research-software/>

⁹ <https://os.helmholtz.de/en/events/fora/6th-forum-research-software/>

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Open Science

2 Program

Friday, 26.09.2025

Time	Program	Speaker
09:00	1. Welcome and Opening Remarks	Mathijs Vleugel, Lea Maria Ferguson, Helmholtz Open Science Office
	2. Introduction to Software Licenses	Tobias Schlauch, DLR
09:30	Session: Rights Management Processes at Helmholtz	
	3. License Guidance within the Helmholtz RSD - Introduction of the Prototype	Christian Meeßen, GFZ
	4. FZJ Open Source Program Office (OSPO)	Ute Schelhaas, FZJ
	5. GFZ Open Source Program Office (OSPO)	Lisa Wenzel, GFZ
	6. Joint Exchange / Comparison between Centers	
10:40	Break	
15:00	Session: Best Practices for Licensing and Rights Allocation	
	7. Open Source Licensing in Research	Tobias Schlauch, DLR
	8. Rights Allocation in Collaborative Projects	Alexander Storm, FZJ
	9. From Open Science to Market Impact: Dual Licensing & Commercializing	Nevine Shalaby, MDC
	10. Joint Discussion	
12:20	Closing Remarks	Lea Maria Ferguson, Helmholtz Open Science Office

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Open Science

3 Presentation Slides

- Helmholtz Quality Indicators for Software- & Data Products by Tobias Schlauch, DLR
- License Guidance within the Helmholtz RSD - Introduction of the Prototype by Christian Meeßen, GFZ
- FZJ Open Source Program Office (OSPO) by Ute Schelhaas, FZJ
- GFZ Open Source Program Office (OSPO) by Lisa Wenzel, GFZ
- Open Source Licensing in Research by Tobias Schlauch, DLR
- Rights Allocation in Collaborative Projects by Alexander Storm, FZJ

INTRODUCTION TO SOFTWARE LICENSES

Research Software Rights Management at Helmholtz, 26.09.2025, Online

Tobias Schlauch <Tobias.Schlauch@DLR.de>

Institute for Software Technology

German Aerospace Center (DLR)

<http://www.dlr.de/sc>

About me

- **Tobias Schlauch, M.Sc. in Computer Science**

- Works as software engineer at DLR and coordinates the DLR Software Engineering Initiative
- Supports DLR researchers in context of the topics open source and software licensing in cooperation with the DLR technology transfer division

Disclaimer:

I am not a lawyer. The presented information result from my practical experiences and are no legal advice. If you need legal advice, please reach out to your legal team.

Copyright basics

- Copyright ([German Copyright Act](#))
 - Copyright protects the expression of an idea and grants exclusive rights (“moral rights of authors”, “exploitation rights”) to the author
 - Software in its source and executed form including its accompanying material is also protected by copyright
- **Who is the author of a software?**
 - All contributors are considered joint authors
 - All authors jointly exercise the rights granted by copyright and decide about the software license!

Software license types

Using code without a license or violating the license obligations can lead to a copyright violation!

Free and Open Source Software Licenses

- **Open Source Software:**

- Characterized by the used software license
- Idea developed in the early 1980s and originates from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology
- Nowadays widespread adoption of open source software in research and industry

- **Free and Open Source Software Licenses:**

- Both terms can be use interchangeable and refer to the [same set of licenses](#)
- Underlying definitions ([Free Software](#), [Open Source Definition](#)) are maintained by the Free Software Foundation and the Open Source Initiative
- Licenses imply the availability of the source code to the users and allow open distribution, modification, and code re-use

**open source
initiative[®]**

OSI and Open Source Initiative are trademarks of Open Source Initiative:
opensource.org.

MIT license – Example of simple permissive Open Source Software License

Copyright <YEAR> <COPYRIGHT HOLDER>

Permission is hereby granted, free of charge, to any person obtaining a copy of this software and associated documentation files (the “Software”), to deal in the Software without restriction, including without limitation the rights to use, copy, modify, merge, publish, distribute, sublicense, and/or sell copies of the Software, and to permit persons to whom the Software is furnished to do so, subject to the following conditions:

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Copyright notice

Granted rights

Obligations

Disclaimer

Copyleft effect

- **Copyleft effect:**

- Adaptations of an existing program must be placed under the open source license of the original program if distributed
- Copyleft is determined by the technical usage and the concrete license

- **Strong vs. weak copyleft:**

- Strong copyleft licenses (e.g., GPL-3.0) require every modification and derivative works to be placed under the license of the original program
- Weak copyleft licenses (e.g., LGPL-3.0) limit the copyleft effect, for example, to modifications of the library itself

- **Consequences:**

- Distribution of your own code under an open source license compatible with the copyleft license
- Potential for license incompatibilities!

Be aware of the consequences of copyleft licenses and consider licenses carefully when selecting libraries!

License compatibility

- **License compatibility** needs to be considered if you combine code under different licenses into one program!

Overview about important Free and Open Source Licenses and their compatibility

Source: David A. Wheeler, [CC BY-SA-3.0](#),

[The Free-Libre / Open Source Software \(FLOSS\) License Slide](#)

License compatibility – Incompatible licenses example

- **License incompatibility** exists when you combine code under different licenses with mutually exclusive license conditions!

Reach out to legal support in “tricky” situations!

Which license should I use for my research software?

- Tips for Free and Open Source Software Licenses:
 - The [EU License Assistant](#) provides a good overview about relevant licenses
 - Prefer [OSI-approved licenses](#)

Summary

- Copyright protects software and grants exclusive rights to the authors
- Free and Open Source Software Licenses are widely used and its important to understand the consequences of their usage
- Software licenses grant rights but also come with obligations:
 - Consider licenses carefully when selecting libraries!
 - Take care when combining code under different licenses!
 - Ask for legal advice if you are unsure with licensing aspects and if copyleft licenses are involved!
- Software license selection ideally supports the transfer strategy for your research software but is influenced by additional constraints!

Copyright and license information

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Thank you!

What are your Questions?

Email: Tobias.Schlauch@dlr.de

Mastodon: <https://norden.social/@schlauch>

HIFIS Mattermost: [@schlauch](#)

License Guidance within the Helmholtz RSD – Introduction of the Prototype

Christian Meeßen

GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences
HIFIS Software Community

7th Helmholtz Open Science Forum Research Software –
Research Software Rights Management at Helmholtz

Online, 26. September 2025

The Helmholtz Research Software Directory

<https://helmholtz.software>

Research Software Directory Search or jump to... Click! Software Projects Organisations Sign in

HELMHOLTZ
Research for grand challenges.

Promote and Discover Research Software
Because software matters

Browse software

Latest news

- CADET**
WEDNESDAY, 17 SEPTEMBER 2025
New Spotlight process and Software Heritage integration
- API Access Tokens**
FRIDAY, 15 AUGUST 2025
Automatically update your software entry via API Access Tokens
- ScienceServe: Boosting Research Software at Helmholtz**
TUESDAY, 29 APRIL 2025
New call for boosting research software at Helmholtz

News archive

The Helmholtz RSD in numbers

415 Registered software packages	1984 Contributors to research software	56298 Mentions of research software in science	220 International partner organisations
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- Online service to collect and present software in an **academic context**
- For **Research Software Engineers**
 - Show impact their software has in research
 - Show relations to organisations, research projects and other software
 - Guide visitors to codebase
- For **Researchers**
 - Discover software they need in their research field
 - Get help for citing code they use
- For **Organisations**
 - Keep track of software
 - Metrics and evaluation

The RSD is open source!

<https://github.com/research-software-directory/RSD-as-a-service>

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository page for 'research-software-directory / RSD-as-a-service'. The repository is public and has 21 forks and 36 stars. The main branch is 'main'. The repository description states: 'This repo contains the new RSD-as-a-service implementation'. The file list includes folders like .github, .vscode, LICENSES, authentication, backend-postgres, backend-tests, background-services, codemeta, data-generation, database, deployment, documentation, e2e, frontend, and mail. The right sidebar shows repository statistics: 36 stars, 21 forks, and 3 releases, with the latest release being v5.3.0.

Fork

Contributions

<https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/research-software-directory/RSD-as-a-service>

The screenshot shows the Codebase repository page for 'RSD-as-a-service'. The repository is public and has 2 unstars and 1 fork. The main branch is 'main'. The repository description states: 'Repository of helmholtz.software'. The file list includes folders like .github, .gitlab, .vscode, LICENSES, authentication, backend-postgres, backend-tests, background-services, codemeta, data-generation, database, deployment, documentation, e2e, and mail. The right sidebar shows repository statistics: 3,781 commits, 8 branches, 70 tags, 446.8 MiB project storage, and 46 releases. The 'Created on' date is March 28, 2023.

The Helmholtz RSD in numbers

415

Registered software packages

1984

Contributors to research software

56298

Mentions of research software in science

220

International partner organisations

The Helmholtz RSD as a service tool for RSEs

License consultation

Example: GFZ consultation process

Perspective of the RSE

RSD: Software-Edit view

Helmholtz Research Software Directory View Software

- Mentions
- Testimonials
- Package managers
- Software Heritage
- Related software
- Related projects
- Maintainers
- Background services
- Obtain a License Consultation**

Software Logo
Upload a logo of your software.

Delete logo

Software Name
Helmholtz Research Software Directory 37/250

Short description
The Helmholtz Research Software Directory is a place to discover and promote research software. Designed for Research Software Engineers and Scientists, it aims to foster FAIR and reuseability of software. 205/300

Description ⓘ

Custom markdown Markdown URL

Markdown Preview 205/10000

Auto-fill

Consultation

RSD - License Consultation

Navigation

- Home
- Personal Info
- Software Info**
- Languages
- Contributors
- Organisations
- Dependencies
- Questionnaire
- Submission

Basic software information

Repository URL * Platform *

Description *

The Helmholtz Research Software Directory is a place to discover and promote research software. Designed for Research Software Engineers and Scientists, it aims to foster FAIR and reuseability of software.

PoF IV

Research Field	Research Program	PoF Topic
5 Information	5.1 Engineering Digital Futures: Supercomputing, Data Management and Information Security for Knowledge and Action	5.1.4 Knowledge for Action

Topic ADD

[PREVIOUS STEP](#) [SAVE AND CONTINUE LATER](#) [NEXT STEP](#)

Example: GFZ consultation process

Perspective of the RSE

Organisation-specific questionnaire

RSD - License Consultation

Navigation

- Home
- Personal Info
- Software Info
- Languages
- Contributors
- Organisations
- Dependencies
- Questionnaire**
- Submission

Questionnaire

Software details

The software is *

New Existing

Can the software be commercialised? *

Yes No

User groups

Please tell us about the target audience of your software ?

Who are the previous users of the software?

Please tell us about the previous user group of the software

Related software

Submit

RSD - License Consultation

Navigation

- Home
- Personal Info
- Software Info
- Languages
- Contributors
- Organisations
- Dependencies
- Questionnaire
- Submission**

Submission

The request can now be submitted. Changes are no longer possible once the form has been sent. Please make sure that everything has been filled in correctly before you continue.

After submitting, notifications will be sent to the following e-mail addresses:

- chmee@gfz.de
- no-reply@gfz.de

[PREVIOUS STEP](#) [SUBMIT](#)

Example: GFZ consultation process

Perspective of the supervisor

Email requests supervisor to review request

RSD - License Consultation

Review

Personal Information

Name	Christian Meeßen
Organisation	GFZ
E-mail	christian.meessen@gfz.de
Phone	123456
Section head	Christian Meeßen
Section head e-mail	chmee@gfz.de

Software Information

Repository Url	https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/research-software-directory/RSD-as-a-service
Platform	gitlab
Description	The Helmholtz Research Software Directory is a place to discover and promote research sc

Topics

Do you want to assign a DOI to your software?

Research Field

5 Informa

Language

Name

Review feedback

Optional comment by the supervisor.

REJECT APPROVE

Example: GFZ consultation process

Perspective of the consultants

RSD - License Consultation

Overview

Notes

Request evaluation: Helmholtz Research Software Directory

Consultation progress

Customer	Christian Meeßen
Supervisor	Christian Meeßen chmee@gfz.de
Date submitted	25/09/2025
Supervisor approval	Yes
License analysis	In progress
Security leaks	Approved
Technology Transfer	In progress
Law department	Not started
Export control	Rejected
Recommendation	Not sent

Content

Personal Information

Name	Christian Meeßen
Organisation	GFZ
E-mail	christian.meessen@gfz.de
Phone	123456

Contact RSEs via email

Track progress for all aspects within the plugin

In progress

Not started

In progress

Approved

Rejected

Example: GFZ consultation process

Perspective of the consultants

RSD - License Consultation

RSD License Consultation
User: Jane Doe

Requests

#	Submitted	Name	Customer	Status
1	25/09/2025	Helmholtz Research Software Directory 🔗	Christian Meeßen	<div>License analysis</div> <div>Security leaks</div> <div>Technology Transfer</div> <div>Law department</div> <div>Export control</div>
2	25/09/2025	Another software 🔗	Thomas Omate	<div>License analysis</div> <div>Security leaks</div> <div>Technology Transfer</div> <div>Law department</div> <div>Export control</div>
3	25/09/2025	Super cool software 🔗	Katharina Ohlrabi	<div>License analysis</div> <div>Security leaks</div> <div>Technology Transfer</div> <div>Law department</div> <div>Export control</div>

Overview of all submitted requests

Behind the scenes

- Tailored questionnaires for centres via Helmholtz ID VOs (Virtual Organisations)
- Questionnaire history
- Fallback questionnaires for centres without their own process (e.g. HIFIS Consulting)
- Consultant membership and assignment via Helmholtz ID

The screenshot displays the 'RSD - License Consultation' interface. On the left, the 'Admin Area' contains two menu items: 'Questionnaire Schemes' (highlighted) and 'Questionnaire Fallbacks'. The main content area is titled 'Questionnaire Schemes' and includes the following fields:

- Organisation:** HIFIS
- Use Case:** HIFIS Consulting
- Description:** Standard questionnaire for HIFIS Software consulting
- Default category?:**

Below these fields is a table with the following data:

	Added on	Mail Address	Enabled	Actions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	24/09/2025, 14:20:30	support@hifis.net	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	20/09/2025, 14:19:10	support@hifis.net	-	

At the bottom, there is a button labeled 'Add questionnaire' with a dropdown arrow.

Roadmap

Planned features and availability

- Finalise the current state
- Pass pilot stage at GFZ
- Onboarding of HIFIS Software Consulting
- Long term: onboarding of further centres, if desired
- More automation
 - analysis of private repositories via OAuth or API

Thank you!

FZJ OPEN SOURCE PROGRAM OFFICE (OSPO)

Research Software Rights Management at Helmholtz –
7. Helmholtz Open Science Forum Forschungssoftware

26.09.2025 | UTE SCHELHAAS

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▶ FZJ OSPO

▶ Challenges

▶ Future topics

▶ Questions

SOFTWARE GUIDELINES

“Write down, what applies in Jülich (... but not what is generally valid)”

GUIDELINES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND DISTRIBUTION OF SOFTWARE AT FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JÜLICH

Version 12.1 | Date: 03.11.2022

Guidelines for the development and distribution of software at Forschungszentrum Jülich

Bertuch, Oliver ^{1,*}, Oliveira, Dennis^{1,*},
Schelhaas, Ute^{1,*}, and Storm, Alexander ^{1,*}

¹Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
*Corresponding Author (rse@fz-juelich.de)

Nov 3, 2022
Version 12.1

This work and its supplements is licensed under 4.0.

1 Introduction

Software¹ is a key element of many researchers daily work.

Developed and used in almost all institutes of Forschungszentrum Jülich, its development is part of a creative process, thus generating executable knowledge. Modern publication contexts consist of written publication, data sets, and software, rendering its development to be an integral part of scholarly work. Furthermore, software development is an intellectual achievement protected by copyright and, in the context of research, an independent, first-class product of scientific work.

Until now, Forschungszentrum Jülich did not have a practical or secure framework within which employees could develop software. The board of directors enacted the attached guidelines (version 12.1) by resolution in February 2022. With these, Forschungszentrum Jülich now presents a document (identical in both German and English) that aims to support the development, management, and impact of software that meets high

TOOLS - SOFTWARE GUIDELINES

CHECKLIST FOR THE DISTRIBUTION OF SOFTWARE CODE

Date	
Name of Software Code	
Institute	
Contact	

Find more information and contact persons at <https://intranet.fz-juelich.de/en/topics/rse>
 General contact for Research Software Engineering topics at FZJ: rse@fz-juelich.de

Copyrights and third-party rights

"All copyrights must be held by Forschungszentrum Jülich" and "All authors need to be known".

- All authors of the software code are known and their names can be disclosed.
- All authors have developed the software code as employees of Forschungszentrum Jülich and the rights of use are held by Forschungszentrum Jülich.
If not:
 - Third-party institutions are known.
 - Forschungszentrum Jülich holds rights of use from these third-party institutions in written form.

Contractual obligations and restrictions

- Funding or grant regulations, cooperation agreements, grant agreements, and

Publication/Dissemination of Software Code Decision Tree

Support

Decision-making tools

Find all tools at: [RSE Portal](#)

Interactive Software Guideline Tool

Check on software application classes

Application class of the software

0 3

If you don't know the application class, see the links above to determine it (by table or by decision tree)

Your chosen application class is 2

URL of the git-repository

For software of category 2, the following standards must be fulfilled.

If you assume to fulfill a standard, please tick the corresponding box.

- Consideration of legal aspects
 Consideration of legal aspects (e.g. third-party rights) is an integral part of the software development process and requires appropriate documentation (e.g. copyright notices).
- Usage of version control
 Version control systems and code repositories are used that contain or refer to all components of the software required for its use, and that are used for change management.

PUBLICATIONS DIRECTIVE

2.2 The procedure regulated subsequently in B. (Procedure) is applicable to all scientific publications according to A 2.1, especially in the form of:

- journal articles
- preprints
- Jül-Bericht or articles in a series of works published by Jülich's publishing house
- habilitations
- doctoral theses
- theses such as bachelor's and master's theses (insofar as they are to be published)
- books or book chapters
- conference papers
- **research software**
- research data

RESEARCH SOFTWARE PUBLICATION MONITOR

Publications from the whole JuSER publication database.

<https://go.fzj.de/rse-publication-monitor>

*keywords mentioned in publications in the JuSER database

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JURSE – JÜLICH RSE COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

<https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/rse>

Claire Wyatt
is our Community
Manager for Research
Software Engineering
based at JSC

Claire and her team are working to create
a community for everyone whose role
involves Research Software Engineering

The screenshot shows the JuRSE website homepage. At the top left is the Jülich Forschungszentrum logo. To its right is the page title 'JuRSE'. Below the title is a navigation menu with links: 'The Latest', 'Community Initiatives', 'Resources', 'Collaborations', and 'About'. The main content area features a welcome message: 'Welcome to JuRSE, the community of practice for *scientists who code*'. Below this is a central graphic of a network of nodes connected by lines, with a laptop in the center displaying the text 'BETTER SOFTWARE BETTER RESEARCH'. Surrounding the laptop are several circular icons: a red lightning bolt, a blue brain, a green leaf, a blue person icon, and a blue group of people icon. To the right of the graphic is a paragraph of text: 'JuRSE is a FZJ-wide initiative working to raise **awareness and increase visibility** for scientists who code as well as to **improve good practice of research software**. We aim to promote the **impact on research**, highlighting the increasingly critical and valuable role research software and coding serves here.' Below this is another paragraph: 'We believe that **creating a community** will lead to more recognition and professionalisation at the same time as helping those scientists who code to be part of a professional community of practice.' This is followed by a paragraph: 'The practice of coding in research is known as 'Research Software Engineering' so our community name is Jülich Research Software Engineering = JuRSE.' The final paragraph states: 'Our key visual includes the well-known motto for Research Software Engineering "**Better Software, Better Research**". This motto was created by the Software Sustainability Institute and has since been adopted around the world.' At the bottom of the page, there is a section titled 'Join the Community of Practice!' with the text: 'Joining the JuRSE Community of Practice and getting involved is simple! Let's briefly show you what this community can do for you and what you can do to engage.'

▶ Increase good practice, visibility and awareness

▶ Encourage adoption of the software and publication guidelines

JURSE & FRIENDS = FZJ OSPO

„Mixed bag of people, that stay in their position“

JURSE – JÜLICH RSE COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

Join the community platform (online)

Meet other RSEs at FZJ and Germany!

Join us at JuRSE Open Hours

In-person and online, we're here to help!

JuRSE Code of the Month

A code in the spotlight

JuRSE Newsletters

Read about RSE News, events, blogs and podcasts

JuRSE Travel Grants

Go to an RSE Conference on us!

▶ Increase good practice, visibility and awareness

▶ Encourage adoption of the software and publication guidelines

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CHALLENGES

- **Resources**
- **Finding the remaining ~ 80% of customers on Campus**
- **Enforcing „voluntary“ guideline vs. „strict“ ruling**
- **Set up own training prgramm**

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FUTURE TOPIC

RSE & RDM

FDM am FZJ: Expertise, Netzwerk, Wandel

Dorit Jerger, Sven Rank

0. Überblick und Status Quo

I. FDM Community Management

Die bislang von der Initiative verschiedener Organisationseinheiten getragenen Bemühungen um die FDM-Community sollen durch eine zentrale Stelle professionalisiert und verstärkt werden.

Aufgaben

- ☑ Eine lebendige FDM-Community im FZJ bilden
- ☑ Dem Jülicher FDM ein Gesicht geben
- ☑ Infos zu FDM-News und Trends verteilen
- ☑ Den FDM-Auftritt des FZJ im Web gestalten
- ☑ Synergien mit der RSE-Community nutzen
- ☑ Konferenzen und Events besuchen und mitgestalten
- ☑ Teil des Netzwerks werden: bei Erfolg arbeiten wir an einer langfristigen Perspektive

Lust mitzugestalten? Wir suchen dich!

II. FDM Expert:innengremium und Netzwerk

Gremium mit regelmäßigem Sitzungsrhythmus, in dem neben dem kollegialen Austausch auch die Beratung strategischer Themen stattfinden soll. Soll bei Bedarf konsentrierte Entscheidungsvorschläge für die Zentrumsleitung ausarbeiten und somit FDM-Prozesse auch in komplizierten Situationen vorantreiben.

III. FDM Challenges

Jährlicher Call für Inhouse-Projekte, bei dem Institute bislang große Freiheit zur Beschreibung einer FDM-Herausforderung sowie eines Lösungsvorschlags hatten. Soll FDM lokal stärken sowie FDM-Experten in Instituten sowie in zentralen Einheiten durch aktive Zusammenarbeit vernetzen. Finanziert durch den Vorstand des Forschungszentrums.

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION !

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cl.wyatt@fz-juelich.de

Open Science Program Office at GFZ

Lisa Wenzel

Transfer & Innovation

7. Helmholtz Open Science Forum Research Software

26.09.2025

GFZ Helmholtz-Zentrum
für Geoforschung

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Research software @GFZ

- Research software is essential for **scientific progress** & inherits also an **innovative potential** for application outside academia
- Sustainable use and development of research software are integral to maintaining good **scientific practice** & enable **knowledge and technology transfer**

The software legal team

- Established and improved a policy and corresponding guidelines for use and licensing of research software
 - Implemented recommended practices
 - Provide advice and support on research software topics
 - Knowledge and technology transfer of research software (assessments, dissemination options)
- Develop and execute an comprehensive strategy dealing with research software at our centre

- > 90% Open Source Software

Software Legal team became OSPO!

Open Source Program Office (OSPO)*:

- is a cross-functional, organizational unit (or team) ✓
- whose mission is to enable, coordinate, and steer an organisation's open source software strategy, policy, practices, and culture **and dissemination** ✓
- its purpose is to support use, contribution, and publishing of open source software in a responsible, sustainable, and strategic fashion ✓

* OSPO Alliance aligned, <https://ospo-alliance.org/>

Policy & Guideline for research software

Further activities enabling sustainable RS

- Helmholtz Software Research Directory
- Helmholtz Software Award
- RSE Meet-Up's & RSE Ambassadors
- Recommended Practices for sustainable software development, drafts for license header, CLA,...
- Innovation projects to validate research software
- SoftWert project (transfer)

helmholtz.software

softwert.org

Research software @ GFZ - Video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r3hSzbEKzjs>

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Source: AI-generated/ChatGPT

OPEN SOURCE LICENSING IN RESEARCH

Research Software Rights Management at Helmholtz, 26.09.2025, Online

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About me

- **Tobias Schlauch, M.Sc. in Computer Science**

- Works as software engineer at DLR and coordinates the DLR Software Engineering Initiative
- Supports DLR researchers in context of the topics open source and software licensing in cooperation with the DLR technology transfer division

Disclaimer:

I am not a lawyer. The presented information result from my practical experiences and are no legal advice. If you need legal advice, please reach out to your legal team.

Typical question in software license consultations

Can we provide <SOFTWARE> under <LICENSE> to
<EXTERNAL AUDIENCE> in this <FORMAT>?

**Distribution of
software to third-
parties typical
triggers license
conditions!**

Step 1: Check that you have the required “rights”

What will be distributed?

The “Software”

Name	Last commit
code	
data	
results	
.gitignore	
.gitlab-ci.yml	
README.md	

astronauts.json

Age distribution, Dead vs. Alive astronauts

Age

Category

boxplot.png

Dead vs. Alive astronauts

Number of astronauts

Age

combined_histogram.png

Total time female humans have spend in space

accumulated_time_in_days

Years

female_humans_in_space.png

Total time humans have spend in space

accumulated_time_in_days

Years

humans_in_space.png

main.py

Do we have the required “rights”?

Step 1: Check that you have the required “rights”

Potential problems and preventive measures

Potential problems:

- Unclear authorship situation
 - Who contributed at all?
 - Under which contractual situation has this person contributed this code?
- Unclear license of file(s)
 - Under which license is this logo?
 - Is this AI generated code a copy of a GPL licensed code?

Preventive measures:

- Contract management: employees, project partners, students, ...
- Documentation:
 - Use a version control system
 - Document all authors and licenses ideally in a machine readable way
 - Document AI usage
- Use snippet scanning tools

The “Software”

Step 1: Check that you have the required “rights”

Documentation with REUSE Software

- **Goal:** Make it easy to determine license and copyright information of source code!
- Heavily builds on SPDX:
<https://spdx.dev/>
- Provides the reuse helper tool for annotation, validation, and more:
<https://git.fsfe.org/reuse/tool>
- For more information: [Tutorial](#), [FAQ](#), [Specification](#)


```
1 # SPDX-FileCopyrightText: 2018 German Aerospace Center (DLR)
2 #
3 # SPDX-License-Identifier: Apache-2.0
4
5 """The standalone script analyzes the astronaut data sets."""
```

Step 2: Check the license compatibility

Basic approach:

- Find out the individual program(s)
- Find out the concretely used software libraries and their licenses for each individual program
- Analyse license compatibility for each individual program

Step 2: Check the license compatibility

Technical usage and copyleft effect of GPL licensed code

- **Clear cases:**

- Copying GPL-licensed code usually triggers copyleft effect
- Inter-process communication with GPL-licensed program (e.g. via pipes / sockets) usually does not trigger the copyleft effect
- GPL-licensed system libraries (e.g., operating system and other runtimes) usually do not trigger the copyleft effect

- **Controversial case:** Linking to GPL-licensed software libraries / plugins / modules:

- Free Software Foundation generally considers linking (statically and dynamically) to trigger the copyleft effect
- Recommendation: Avoid this “grey area” and follow this interpretation

Step 2: Check the license compatibility

Potential problems and preventive measures

Potential problems:

- Unclear which individual programs exist
- Unclear list of dependencies and how they are used
- Mixing program and development dependencies
- Wrong license metadata in used software libraries

Preventive measures:

- Clear dependency selection process:
 - Make license a selection criteria
 - Check relevant sub-dependencies and options as well
- Document dependencies and use a package manager
- Use license scanners/linters: ecosystem-specific vs. generic tools

Step 2: Check the license compatibility

OSS Review Toolkit

- [OSS Review Toolkit](#) provides a set of tools to support license compliance
 - Supports different tools in each analysis step, for example, [ClearlyDefined](#) as a license fact database
 - Supports curation and flexible definition of evaluation policies
 - Supports many standard report formats (NOTICE file, SPDX, CycloneDX, ...)
- Generic approach which requires a bit of setup work
- More suited for building an organization-wide solution

The screenshot shows the OSS Review Toolkit interface. On the left, a tree view displays the dependency graph starting with 'PyPI:pandas:2.3.2'. The main panel shows the details for 'PyPI:pandas:2.3.2', including a 'Licenses' section with 'Effective SPDX' and 'Declared' licenses, and a 'Scan Results' table.

Value	Path	Start	End
Copyright (c) 2011-2012, PyData Development Team	pandas-2.3.2/AUTHORS.md	12	12

Screenshot of a report for further analysis of the evaluation results

Step 3: Consider the influence of the distribution format on license obligations

- **Source distributions:**

- Examples: Source code package on PyPi / Git repository on GitHub
- Make sure to provide copyright and license information for the distributed files (see also: [REUSE Software](#))
- Checking license compatibility is still relevant in this case!

- **Binary distributions:**

- Examples: Installer / archive with compiled binaries / container image
- Provide copyright and license information for your own (binary) files
- Fulfil the licensing obligations of distributed binary code of third-parties:
 - Many open source licenses require to provide copyright notices and licenses
 - Copyleft licenses usually require to provide the corresponding code
 - [DLR Open Source Brochure](#) (German only) provides a good overview of these requirements for selected open source licenses
 - Container images impose their special challenges!

Summary

- Distributing a software under a specific license to a third-party imposes different challenges. Typically, you need to:
 - Check that you have the required “rights”
 - Check the license compatibility of the individual programs
 - Consider the influence of the distribution format on license obligations
- It is recommended to follow a risk-based approach and to make use of proper tool support to manage the complexity of license compatibility checks
- Many challenges can be addressed early but require proper organizational polices, support, and awareness!

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Thank you!

What are your Questions?

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Mastodon: <https://norden.social/@schlauch>

HIFIS Mattermost: [@schlauch](#)

Rights Allocation in Collaborative Projects

Disclaimer: People are different

What are Rights?

- depends on the rule of law in contract
- US/UK: basically everything / most of EU: only use and utilization

non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free...to make, use,

→ necessary? US/UK: Yes / EU: No

How to allocate?

- allocation regulated within Project
 - DESCA? (https://www.desca-agreement.eu/assets/helmholtz_gemeinschaft/user_upload/Brussels_Office/DESCA/20240206_DESCA_HorizonEurope_v.2.0_with_elucidations.pdf)
 - MODULE IPR SC → best avoid, at least don't modify or just choose a licence

For the avoidance of doubt...

Who can allocate?

- Normal people? → No! Organisations (Employers)
- anything you create within your line of work belongs to your employer
 - How can i be sure the person is allowed to allocate rights?
- Within the project you are safe

Who can allocate?

- What happens after the Project?
- Use for scientific purpose (Copyright Act, AI Act Def...?)
- Reasonable payment?
- What about externals?

All hail the CLA!

- Contributor Licence Agreement
- FZJ Template (<https://iffmd.fz-juelich.de/KspEDw-DQqO09przP6bbGQ#>)

Thanks and keep your contracts simple.

HELMHOLTZ

Open Science